

moist filter paper in petri plates. A minimum 50% mortality was obtained from all isolates, and at least 70% for *S. felitae* isolates. There was no mortality in untreated crickets.

In tests using the same methods with other lepidoptera and hymenoptera, such as honey bees and ants, mortality was less than 10%. Using the methods with field crickets *Gryllus* sp. and short-tailed crickets *Anurogryllus* sp. gave infectivity rates in excess of 50%.

These results indicate that these nematode strains are highly host-specific and extremely infective to mole, field, and short-tailed crickets. As these strains were isolated from sandy riverbanks and from mole cricket populations, their potential use for the major pest species of the Amazon, *Scapteriscus didactylus* Scudder, as well as for locally troublesome species of mole crickets seems highly promising, especially in the Amazon, where mole cricket densities are high, and there are no registered control insecticides. □

Neem seed kernel or neem cake powder and carbofuran granule mixture for controlling green leafhopper (GLH) and rice tungro virus (RTV)

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Carbofuran granules at 2 kg ai/ha are often applied as a prophylactic measure to rice in RTV-prone areas. Insecticidal control relying on economic threshold levels for the vector GLH *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) is risky.

Neem seed derivatives have been found to reduce GLH feeding and RTV transmission. They reportedly possess antimicrobial activity that may reduce the degradation of carbofuran in flooded rice soils.

We tested neem seed kernel and neem cake powder mixed with carbofuran at 1 kg ai/ha (33.3 kg neem powder: 33.3 kg Furadan 3G) against carbofuran

Mortality of GLH adults, nymph emergence, and RTV infection in TN1 plants treated with carbofuran mixed with neem seed kernel (NSK) or neem cake (NC) powder or with carbofuran alone.^a IIRRI, 1987.

Treatment	Adult mortality (%) in infestations		Nymphs emerged (no.)	RTV infection (%)
	1st	2d		
Carbofuran (1 kg ai/ha) + NSK (1:1)	100 a	100 a	0 a	2 a
Carbofuran (1 kg ai/ha) + NC (1:1)	98 a	96 a	0 a	8 b
Carbofuran (2 kg ai/ha)	100 a	100 a	0 a	10 b
Carbofuran (1 kg ai/ha)	100 a	98 a	4 b	28 c
Untreated (control)	0 b	0 b	285 c	100 d

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. Av of 5 replications.

at 2 kg ai/ha (66.6 kg Furadan 3G). Because neem trees are widespread in many rice-growing countries, neem-carbofuran mixtures could appreciably reduce the cost of purchased inputs for RTV management.

Powdered neem seed kernel and cake from 1987 harvest were mixed separately (1:1 wt/wt) with carbofuran in polythene bags. The neem-carbofuran mix or carbofuran alone was applied at 2 kg ai/ha to 1-mo-old potted GLH- and RTV-susceptible TN1 rice plants. Untreated plants and plants treated with carbofuran at 1 kg ai/ha were the controls.

At 24 h after treatment, 5 pairs of viruliferous GLH males and females were caged on treated and control plants. Insect mortality was measured

72 h after infestation and used GLH adults were removed and replaced with 5 pairs of fresh viruliferous adults. Insect mortality was measured 72 h after reinfestation. Nymph emergence was observed daily from 1 wk after first infestation to 10 d after reinfestation. RTV infection based on visual symptoms was measured 20 d after reinfestation.

Insect mortality was 98-100% with carbofuran alone, 96-100% in the neem-carbofuran mixtures, and 0 in the control (see table). Nymph emergence in the carbofuran treatments significantly differed from that in the control. Carbofuran mixed with neem seed kernel powder was most effective against RTV, keeping infection to 2%. □

Sensitivity of different stages of *Leptocorisa oratorius* (Fabricius) to monocrotophos

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Nymphs and adults of *L. oratorius*, the most widely distributed rice bug species, damage rice from flowering through the dry dough stage. A common control method is the use of insecticides. To be more efficient, insecticide should be applied not only at the stage when the pests do the most damage to rice, but also when the insects are most sensitive to the treatment. We tested five nymphal instars and female adults to

LD₅₀, values for reaction of different life stages of *Leptocorisa oratorius* to monocrotophos. IIRRI, 1987.

Stage	LD ₅₀ ^a	
	µg/g	µg/insect
First instar	0.52 c	0.70 a
Second instar	0.62 c	1.70 b
Third instar	0.56 c	4.85 c
Fourth instar	0.89 d	16.24 e
Fifth instar	0.37 b	39.11 f
Adult female	0.06 a	9.13 d

^aLD₅₀s followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

determine the insect stage most sensitive to insecticides.

Insects collected in vials from culture cages were anaesthetized with CO₂.

Monocrotophos was applied topically at 0.5 µl, using a Burkard microapplicator with calibrated microsyringe. Treated insects were transferred to rice panicles of plants enclosed in mylar cages. The test had 10 insects/treatment with 4 replications.

Cages were kept in the phytotron at 27-30 °C, 60-80% relative humidity, and 12 h illumination. Mortality was recorded 24 h after treatment. LD₅₀

values were computed using probit analysis.

The lowest LD₅₀ value (µg/g) was for adult females and the highest for the 4th instar (see table). Regardless of body weight, the adult was more sensitive than the 4th and 5th instar. Lower insecticide dosages will control adults; higher dosages may be needed to control nymphs. □

Susceptibility of brown planthopper (BPH) and green leafhopper (GLH) to insecticides under different temperatures

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When LD₅₀ values are compared between locations, prevailing temperature could cause inconsistent results. We subjected BPH and GLH to six different temperatures after topical insecticide application.

Serial dosages of 7 insecticides were prepared in acetone solution and 0.1 µl and applied on the thoracic tergites of anaesthetized BPH and 0.2 µl on those of GLH. Twenty treated adults were placed in a plastic tumbler, provided with 10 two-week-old seedlings for food,

and transferred in Koitotron cabinets set at constant temperatures of 18 °C to 33 °C with natural daylength. Insect mortality was recorded 24 h after treatment and LD₅₀ values were computed using probit analysis.

BPH and GLH were susceptible to most of the insecticides at higher temperatures and to the pyrethroids at lower temperatures (see table). For BPH, all insecticides except cypermethrin and deltamethrin had lower LD₅₀ values at 33 °C than at 18 °C (see table). For GLH, all insecticides except carbaryl and the two pyrethroids were more potent at higher temperatures. Insecticide activity was comparable at the temperature range 27-30 °C. Temperatures before, during, and after treatment should be recorded to control their possible effect on insecticide activity. □

LD₅₀ values of BPH brachypterous adult females and GLH adult females at 6 temperatures. ^a IRRI phytotron, 1987.

Temp (°C)	LD ₅₀ (µg/g) in 24 h						
	BPMC	Carbaryl	Carbofuran	Cypermethrin	Deltamethrin	Diazinon	Malathion
<i>BPH</i>							
18	4.68 a	4.12 a	1.19 a	0.24 a	0.40 a	12.13 a	37.43 a
21	2.59 b	4.64 a	0.85 ab	0.25 a	0.53 a	8.36 a	23.95 a
24	1.92 b	3.91 a	0.74 abc	0.29 a	0.46 a	8.46 a	27.02 a
27	1.30 b	3.78 a	0.37 bc	0.33 a	0.57 a	6.76 a	14.38 a
30	1.70 b	4.08 a	0.39 bc	0.42 a	0.55 a	7.05 a	13.95 a
33	0.61 b	1.67 b	0.21 c	0.39 a	0.59 a	4.92 a	9.08 a
<i>GLH</i>							
18	6.85 a	4.38 a	3.42 a	0.14 b	0.12 b	36.20 a	11.83 a
21	7.00 a	5.38 a	2.88 ab	0.21 ab	0.27 b	27.61 b	12.05 a
24	4.40 ab	4.54 a	2.03 bc	0.14 b	0.54 ab	23.78 b	12.25 a
27	3.49 b	5.62 a	1.61 bc	0.25 ab	0.75 a	19.04 b	9.62 ab
30	2.30 b	3.70 a	1.68 bc	0.58 a	0.75 a	19.10 b	9.31 ab
33	1.66 b	4.41 a	1.17 c	0.57 a	0.71 a	19.36 b	6.99 b

^a Av of 3 replications, 20 insects/replication. In a column within a species, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Residues of quinalphos in rice

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We studied residues of quinalphos (0, 0-diethyl-D-[2-quinoxaly] phosphorothionate), widely used insecticide, in rice variety Lalat (ORS26-2014). The pesticide was sprayed at the recommended level (0.05%, or 0.25 kg ai/ha) and double the recommended level (0.1%, or 0.50 kg ai/ha). Plant samples were collected at 0, 10, 20, and 30 d after spraying and at harvest.

The spectrophotometric method was used to estimate residues of quinalphos, using p-nitrobenzyl pyridine as the chromogenic reagent. Recovery of quinalphos from fortified plant samples was 86-87%.

Mean initial residues of 1.04 ppm (0.05%) and 18.86 ppm (0.1%) were reduced to 3.45 and 6.86 ppm 10 d after insecticide application, to 0.62 and 1.05 ppm 20 d after application, and to nondetectable levels 30 d after

Linear plot of first-order reaction of quinalphos in rice. Bhubaneswar, India.